

Craniofacial Deformities

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Craniofacial deformities (CFA) includes deformities in the head and facial bones. Such abnormalities are developed since birth. Some are mild deformities while others are severe and they require reconstructive surgery.

There are several factors which contribute to the facial abnormality discussed as below:

- **Genetic cause.** A child may get a gene(s) from parents. Or the genes may change at the time of conception. This may be a cause of craniofacial deformity in a child.
- **Environmental cause.** Environmental exposures may play a role, in combination with genetic deformities.
- **Folic acid deficiency.** Folic acid is a Vitamin B found in orange juice, fortified breakfast cereals, enriched grain products, and green, leafy vegetables. Studies have shown that women who do not consume it during pregnancy, may have a higher risk of having a baby with certain congenital anomalies. These include cleft lip and cleft palate.

Some of the most common types of craniofacial deformities include the following:

Cleft lip and cleft palate are the most common congenital craniofacial deformities seen at birth.

- **Cleft Lip.** An abnormality in which the lip does not completely form. The degree of the cleft lip can vary greatly, from mild (notching of the lip) to severe (large opening from the lip up through the nose).
- **Cleft Palate.** Happens when the mouth does not completely close, leaving an opening that can extend into the nasal cavity. The cleft may involve either side of the palate. It can extend from the front of the mouth (hard palate) to the throat (soft palate). The cleft may also include the lip.
 - **Craniosynostosis.** A condition in which the sutures

(soft spots) in the skull of an infant close too early. This causes problems with normal brain and skull growth. Premature closure of the sutures may also cause the pressure inside of the head to increase and the skull or facial bones to change from a normal, symmetrical appearance.

- **Hemifacial Microsomia.** Hemifacial microsomia is also known as Goldenhar syndrome, brachial arch syndrome, facio-auriculo-vertebral syndrome, oculo-auriculo-vertebral spectrum, or lateral facial dysplasia. A condition in which the tissues on one side of the face are underdeveloped. This mostly affects the ear (aural), mouth (oral), and jaw (mandibular) areas. Sometimes, both sides of the face can be affected and may involve the skull and the face.
- **Vascular Malformation.** It can cause functional or aesthetic problems. Vascular malformations may involve multiple body systems. There are several different types of malformations and they are named according to which type of blood vessel is mostly affected.
- **Hemangioma.** A hemangiomas is an abnormally growing blood vessel in the skin that may be since birth or appear in the first months after birth. A hemangioma is also known as a port wine stain, strawberry hemangioma, and salmon patch.
- **Deformational (or Positional) Plagiocephaly.** A asymmetrical shape of the head from repeated pressure to the same area of the head.

Therefore we conclude that Craniofacial abnormalities are birth defects of the face or head. Treatment depends on the type of problem. Plastic and reconstructive surgery may help the person's appearance.